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**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. D1.1

**Organisation and minutes of the first EU Polar cluster
meeting**

Submission of Deliverable

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1 Introduction

At the meeting of the EU Arctic Cluster in June 2019, it was agreed that we would extend the membership of the Cluster to polar and Antarctic projects. With this scope, EU-PolarNet, and subsequently EU-PolarNet 2, are leading the coordination of this Cluster, within Work Package 1, task 1.1.

This deliverable is the organisation and delivery of the 1st EU Polar Cluster meeting, and therefore consists of the contents for a meeting report: header page, agenda, and minutes of the meeting.

Meeting Report

Rapporteur: Elaina Ford

Meeting details:	
Name of the conference / workshop	EU Polar Cluster Annual Meeting 2020
Date and location	27 th October 2020, online
EU-PolarNet 2 participant(s)	All
Attendees	Please see section 3.3 for list of (virtual) participants for the closed section of the meeting. There were 340 attendees signed into the open sessions. The names of these individuals cannot be shared by the ESA organisers due to GDPR.
Agenda	Please see 0 Agenda
Meeting objectives	To welcome new projects to the EU Polar Cluster, update on new leadership through EU PolarNet 2, and update projects on the work of the Task Groups.
Role of EU-PolarNet 2	Organisation and delivery.
Meeting outcome / comments	Please see section 3 Minutes
Action Items	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sign up to Horizon Results Booster web platform and complete questionnaire, by 3rd November. All projects• Use #EUPolarCluster in social media. Ongoing. All projects• Set up monthly tea/coffee sessions for the Cluster – Elaina Ford• Organise follow up meetings for each of the task groups, in addition to the annual meetings – Task Group co-leads• Organise a workshop on impacts of Covid-19 on the projects – Renuka Badhe.• Send poll for Policy Task Group – David Velazquez

2 Agenda

ESA and EU Polar Clusters Day

EU Polar Cluster Annual Meeting 2020

Agenda

Tuesday, 27th October 2020 (09:00 – 18:00h CET) – Virtual Meeting

09:00 – 10:30	Highlights of EU Polar Cluster Projects – Public part <i>Chair: Renuka BADHE (European Polar Board, The Netherlands)</i>
09:00 – 09:20	Opening words by Sigi GRUBER, Head of Unit, European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Healthy Oceans Unit and Arnoldas MILUKAS, Head of Unit, EASME, H2020 Environment and Resource Unit
09:20– 09:30	Strengthening cooperation across disciplines: The EU Polar Cluster by Nicole BIEBOW (AWI, Germany)
09:30 – 09:45	Improving the accuracy of climate predictions in the Northern Hemisphere by Thomas JUNG (AWI, Germany). <i>Projects: APPLICATE, BLUE-Action, INTAROS.</i>
09:45 – 09:55	Short break.
09:55 – 10:05	Enhancing the European capacity in Earth Observation for the monitoring of the Polar Regions by Nick HUGHES (Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Norway) <i>Project: KEPLER.</i>
10:05 – 10:20	Assessing the socioeconomic impact of a changing Arctic by Alexandra MEYER (University of Vienna, Austria) <i>Projects: EU-PolarNet, iCUPE, NUNATARYUK.</i>
10:20 – 10:30	Obtaining a 1.5-million-year-old ice-core from East Antarctica to improving climate projections by Carlo BARBANTE (ISP-CNR, Italy) <i>Project: Beyond-EPICA.</i>
10:30– 10:45	Making the Arctic accessible to all European researchers by Margareta JOHANSSON (Lund University, Sweden) <i>Projects: ArcSAR, ARICE, INTERACT and SIOS.</i>
10:45 – 11:00	Short break
11:00 – 12:30	Introduction to the New Polar Cluster Projects – Public part (cont.) <i>Chair: Elaina FORD (British Antarctic Survey, UK)</i>
11:00 – 11:15	The EU Polar Cluster: Objectives and activities by David VELAZQUEZ (AWI, Germany)

11:15 – 11:30	The ESA Polar Science Cluster by Diego Fernandez (ESA, Italy)
11:30 – 12:30	<p>Widening the cooperation: the new EU Polar Cluster projects</p> <p>ECOTIP. Arctic biodiversity change and its consequences: Assessing, monitoring and predicting the effects of ecosystem tipping cascades on marine ecosystem services and dependent human systems by Marja KOSKI (DTU, Denmark)</p> <p>FACE-IT. The future of Arctic coastal ecosystems - Identifying transitions in fjord systems and adjacent coastal areas by Kai BISCHOF (University of Bremen, Germany)</p> <p>CHARTER. Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity by Bruce FORBES (University of Lapland, Finland)</p> <p>Health break</p>
11:40 – 11:50	<p>PROTECT. PROjecTing sEa-level rise : from iCe sheets to local implicaTions by Gaël DURAND (CNRS,IGE, France)</p> <p>ArcticHubs. Global drivers, local consequences: Tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic “hubs” by Pasi RAUTIO (Luke, Finland)</p> <p>JUSTNORTH. Toward Just, Ethical and Sustainable Arctic Economies, Environments and Societies by Corine WOOD-DONNELLY (Uppsala University, Sweden)</p> <p>CAPARDUS. Capacity-building in Arctic standardisation development by Stein SANDVEN (NERSC, Norway)</p> <p>SO-CHIC. Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate by Jean-Baptiste SALLÉE (CNRS, LOCEAN-IPSL, France)</p> <p>TIPACCs. Tipping Points in Antarctic Climate Components by Petra LANGEBROEK (NORCE, Norway)</p> <p>FORCeS. Constrained aerosol forcing for improved climate projections by Annica EKMAN (Stockholm University, Sweden)</p>
12:20 – 12:30	Panel Q&A
12:30 – 13:30	<i>Virtual Lunch break</i>
13:30 – 15:00	ESA POLAR SCIENCE CLUSTER – Public part <i>Chairs: Larisa Lorinczi (EC) and Ola Grabak (ESA)</i>
14:30-14:35	ESA/EC Introduction
14:35-15:10	Round Table discussion: René Forsberg (DTU)

15:10-15:20	Johnny A. Johannessen (NERCS)
15:20-15:30	Nicole Biebow (AWI)
15:30-15:40	Jouni Pulliainen (FMI)
15:40-15:50	4D Antarctica Noel Gourmelen (University of Edinburgh) -
15:50-16:00	Polar+ 4D Greenland Louise Sandberg Sørensen (DTU) -
	Polar+ Ice Shelves Anna Hogg (University of Leeds)
	ARKTALAS Johnny A. Johannessen (NERCS)
	METHEO Lindqvist Hannakaisa (FMI)
<i>15:00 – 15:30</i>	<i>Virtual Coffee break</i>
<i>15:30 – 18:00</i>	Closed part of the EU Polar Cluster Annual Meeting 2020 <i>Chair: Nicole BIEBOW & David VELAZQUEZ (AWI, Germany)</i>
15:30 – 15:40	Welcome words by Gaëlle LE BOULER (EASME)
15:40 – 15:50	EU-PolarNet 2 role in the EU Polar Cluster by Nicole BIEBOW (AWI, Germany)
15:50 – 16:00	Common Dissemination Booster –Pre-assessment of the EU Polar Cluster (TBC)
16:00 – 16:40	Presentations by the Polar Cluster members on the progress on the 4 Task Groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication by Elaina FORD (BAS, UK) - Stakeholder engagement by Annette SCHEEPSTRA (RUG, The Netherlands) & Kirsi LATOLA (UOULU, Finland) - Education by Josefine LENZ (APECS, Germany) & Katharina BECKMANN (Lund University, Sweden) - Data management by Øysten GODOY (Met. Norway) & Stein SANDVEN (NERSC Norway)
16:40 – 16:50	Short break
16:50 – 17:45	Interactive discussion on e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Future and engagement of Cluster projects - Discussion on the Task Groups and potential new Task Groups - Communications and dissemination within the EU Polar Cluster - Any other business
17:45 – 18:00	Summary discussion Next steps and future meetings

3 Minutes

3.1 Highlights of EU Polar Cluster Projects

Chair: Renuka Badhe (*European Polar Board, The Netherlands*)

Time: 09:00 – 10:45 CET

Rapporteur: Elaina Ford

Attendees: ~340

3.1.1 Opening words

- By **Sigi GRUBER**, Head of Unit, European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Healthy Oceans Unit
- S. Gruber gave a very warm welcome and thanked those from EC, EASME and EU-PolarNet, and all the projects in the EU and ESA Polar Clusters.
- In a world of tremendous change and multiple crises with economic recession and covid-19, which impact the lives of people and of the Arctic and the oceans.
- Arctic human communities are adapting to climate change, but both internal and external stressors are challenging this adaptation. We cannot neglect this and must put people first. We therefore must discuss results.
- Polar changes have consequences for the entire planet.
- The enhanced collaboration with ESA is very important to the EC. Adapting to change is a key political priority. The EU green deal is the compass of Europe's recovery to create a greener, fairer, and more resilient society.
- Climate related research is also very high on the agenda of Horizon Europe. Missions on healthier ocean coasts and inland waterways, and on climate adaptation and transformation of society, are at the heart of the climate agenda. This will be co-created and rolled out in due course.
- Policy will be based on science evidence, through improvements of models, IPCC, and events such as with European Parliament.

- There is an open [consultation on EU Arctic Policy](#) to improve the link between science and policy, which is open until the 10th November. (Action – all)
 - The Antarctic is increasing an area of focus for the EC, which is supporting CCAMLR (Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources), MPA (Marina Protected Areas).
- And **Arnoldas MILUKAS**, Head of Unit, EASME, H2020 Environment and Resource Unit
- This is an urgent need, as noted in the State of the Union speech, to accelerate our actions to protect the planet, and the EC's Green Deal is a blueprint to make that transformation.
- EC has published, in September, a [Green Deal call](#) through H2020 with a budget of nearly €1B
- The IPCC's SSROC (Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere) report noted reducing greenhouse emissions will reduce cryosphere changes, therefore the livelihood of those that live there can be preserved. EU has a call to support the Green Deal.
- EU and EASME supported two meetings of the EU Arctic Cluster in 2018 and 2019.
- To support the extension to the EU Polar Cluster, EU PolarNet 2 has a coordinating role in managing this.

3.1.2 Strengthening cooperation across disciplines: The EU Polar Cluster

- By Nicole BIEBOW (AWI, Germany)
- N. Biebow coordinates EU PolarNet 2, ARICE, and represents Germany at SAON.
- Priority area from EU policy for the Arctic – Climate change and safeguarding the Arctic environment, sustainable development in and around the Arctic, International Cooperation on the Arctic.
- Following the H2020 work plans, we decided with the EU to collaborate to avoid duplication and increase cooperation. There were initially 8 projects: EU-PolarNet, Application, Blue Action, ARICE, ICE-ARC, INTERACT, NUNATARYUK, INTAROS.
- EU funding however was addressing further priorities, such as the Paris Agreement and SDGs, so we enlarged the project also to include upcoming calls including polar projects. Thanks to the EU this group is still growing and future call projects will be included.
- EPB and SIOS are also strongly involved in in Cluster
- Objectives
 - Creating synergies
 - Pooling resources
 - Increase knowledge sharing
 - Join activities
- We have four task groups to address these, which will be discussed later.

3.1.3 Improving the accuracy of climate predictions in the Northern Hemisphere

- By Thomas JUNG (AWI, Germany).

- Projects: APPLICATE, BLUE-Action, INTAROS.
- Head Polar Predictions at AWI
- Goals of projects:
 - APPLICATE – develop advance predictive capacity in Polar Regions and beyond;
 - BLUE-Action – Investigate the effect of a changing Arctic on weather and climate;
 - INTAROS – Develop an efficient integrated Arctic Observation System
- Some highlight results:
 - Skilful seasonal predictions can be produced
 - Seasonal and decadal climate predictions including sea ice improves mid latitude temperature.
 - Decadal projections can be improved due to saline circulation. Ocean overturning can be prediction for winter sea surface temperature.
 - Whether Arctic amplification can explain mid-latitude winter extreme weather events such as heat waves and droughts is still a matter for research. Collaboration between the projects are working to address this, showing Arctic Amplification is warming the lower latitudes.
- See conclusions slide
- Skilful prediction of sea ice on seasonal to decadal timescales is possible (“bright prospects”)
- North Atlantic climate has better predictions on the inter annual and decadal time scales
- Exploiting the full potential of underlying predictability requires further investments in understanding, observations, models and data assimilation.
- Message for policy makers. A further major leap could be taken through further investment in observation, to reduce errors and biases in instrumentation. Digital twins with a polar component would be beneficial. The learning curve is still quite steep so listen to the science coming out.

3.1.4 Enhancing the European capacity in Earth Observation for the monitoring of the Polar Regions

- By Nick HUGHES (Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Norway)
- Project: KEPLER – Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness
- H2020 Coordination and Support Action (CSA) 2.25 years, €2.9M, 15 partners, started 1st January 2019.
- Main focus is looking into the future of Copernicus. Main aims to develop a roadmap of European capacity particularly in the Arctic, and bringing the components of marine service, climate service, atmosphere, and land services (CMEMS, C3S, CAMS, CLMS) beyond the present state of the art and help increase the user base.
- The users of Copernicus are central to the project and WP structure.
- WP1 sub-tasks covered a range of groups needs,
 - maritime and research sector – needs have been stable and polling not improving information products;

- high-latitude communications is an increasing issue with increased data volumes
 - nearer real-time higher spatial resolution products needed, in common data formats, not netCDF
- WP3 – identification of research and capacity gaps
 - long report on space-based capability needed based on the input from users in WP1.
 - determined requirements for ground-truthing and effects of implementing different options
- Identified 14 parameters not being served by Copernicus EO capacity, and identified parameters for future missions
- Need more dialogue between European polar research and monitoring community and Copernicus services, and needs coordination.
- Recommendations for improvements on covering requirements and different spatial/temporal scales; harmonisation of products; coordination of ECV suppliers; forecast resolution and quality to be improved.
- Ongoing work on end-to-end operational roadmap (synthesis of WPs 1-4), which will cover all components of that system.
- Training workshop with CMEMS on 1st December – all welcome
- www.kepler-polar.eu – sign up to mailing list, access deliverables. @KeplerEU

3.1.5 Assessing the socioeconomic impact of a changing Arctic

- By Alexandra MEYER (University of Vienna, Austria)
- Projects: EU-PolarNet, iCUPE, NUNATARYUK.
- With 7 million people living in the Arctic, so research focussed on socioeconomic impacts of change.
- iCUPE has produced 21 datasets to date (available), with more in the pipeline.
 - Survey on how permafrost thaw in explaining some of the indigenous people's challenges. Links to SDGs.
- NUNATARYUK is an interdisciplinary project on community-based research and modelling.
 - What changes and impacts are important to them, not necessarily in line with the science; both need to be considered.
 - Three study sites Nordic areas, Beaufort Sea, East Siberia area. Areas have different societal priorities and impacts
- EU PolarNet – connecting science with society
 - White paper on stakeholder survey, sent in nine languages, highlighted that an online survey doesn't reach many indigenous people so future surveys should think about format.
 - The results were combined to the Integrated European Polar Research Programme. This was co-designed by the indigenous communities, which is a valuable and critical aspect of any research in their area.
 - Outreach and science communications is crucial. Networks and collaboration are particularly important with Arctic communities not to overwhelm them. Must include culture with social and economic in social

science research. Community involvement takes time and trust needs to be built.

3.1.6 Obtaining a 1.5-million-year-old ice-core from East Antarctica to improving climate projections

- By Carlo BARBANTE (ISP-CNR, Italy)
- Project: Beyond-EPICA.
- This is the European effort to obtain an 1.5Myr greenhouse gas – climate feedback record from an ice core in East Antarctica, which builds on EPICA, the European Project of Ice Coring in Antarctica, which showed how the CO₂ levels above 400ppm are above anything in the past.
- Looking particularly at mid-Pleistocene Transition, around 1000kyr ago.
- This is addressing the IPICS first grand challenge on climate and greenhouse gasses from Antarctica. This is a collaboration with eight nations globally, to increase our capacity to understand the climate of the past to how it fits today's climate.
- Aim to retrieve a continuous ice core to bedrock, and derive first high-resolution climate records over 700kyr.
- Previous project investigated locations. Aims now are to drill at Concordia region, 2300km in 2 season of surveys showed best site is 40km from Concordia.
- Will require 5000 person days in the field, 22 tonnes of cargo, 100m³ fuel, a traverse of 80 tonnes and a budget from EU of €11M plus national logistical support. Camp set up this January 2020, drilling was to start this season but is delayed due to Covid-19.
- Collaborations within the EU Polar Cluster aimed with SO-CHIC, TiPACCs, and PROTECT.

3.1.7 Making the Arctic accessible to all European researchers

- By Margareta JOHANSSON (Lund University, Sweden)
- Projects: ArcSAR, ARICE, INTERACT and SIOS.
- INTERACT - legacy – more than 1000 scientists have been awarded TA from interact. With more than 250 publications, contributions to science diplomacy through station visits. Scientists have unique findings, from a new species of bumblebee (named after the project!).
- ARICE will have eight cruises funded. Some work managed during Covid-19 with remote access.
- SIOS, started in 2010, is an international partnership of researchers studying the environment and climate in and around Svalbard. Marine, terrestrial and atmospheric. It has 24 members from 9 different countries.
- So sending people to the Arctic, a dangerous remote environment, you need to be prepared. To this end:
 - INTERACT has prepared two books to assist, the INTERACT Field Planning Handbook and the Practical Field Guide.
 - The EU has funded ARCSAR for professional security and emergency preparedness network in the Arctic and North-Atlantic
- These four projects help to make the Arctic accessible to all European researchers, and beyond.

3.1.8 Discussion:

- Alexandra – impact of Covid-19 on Arctic Communities?
 - From Svalbard perspective, it has had huge economic impacts, as the economy is largely dependent on tourism, leading to job losses.
 - This has created a larger gap between the (often foreigners) working in the service industry, not part of the Norwegian protection support
 - A lot of people have had to leave the island.
- Carlo: we are strongly encouraged towards an output of net zero, have you any comments on this and how it can be tackled for Antarctic research
 - We are very much committed on this. Antarctic operations are very heavy. We are planning compensation actions, which are being built up in the next year.
 - We can also do as much as we can with efficiencies and renewables (wind, solar) where possible.
- Margareta – how much of TA has been affected by the pandemic and what is expected next summer
 - INTERACT – 120 people couldn't go out to summer. The project has been extended a year so we can delay to hope fully next year.
 - Capacity is not a problem as we have 53 stations.
 - SIOS have 13 project they could not accommodate, which they plan on doing next summer, and again should not impact on other projects next year.
 - ARICE has 6 projects that we hope to do next summer. So there should not be a long term impact, if we can go ahead next summer.

Action items:

Complete [consultation on EU Arctic Policy](#) - all – by the 10th November 2020.

3.2 Introduction to the New Polar Cluster Projects

Chair: Elaina Ford (*British Antarctic Survey, UK Research and Innovation*)

Time: 09:00 – 10:45 CET

Rapporteur: Elaina Ford

Attendees: ~340

3.2.1 The EU Polar Cluster: Objectives and activities

- By David VELAZQUEZ (AWI, Germany)
- D. Velazquez is coordinating the EU Polar Cluster, through EU-PolarNet.
- The Cluster is now 21 projects, and two partners, the European Polar Board (EPB) and SIOS, the Svalbard Integrated Observing System.
- The Cluster formally started in 2017 as the EU Arctic Cluster, born out of the need to work together.
- This started as a bottom up initiative through a few projects, and was well received by the EC.
- We collaborate with aims to avoid duplications, and create synergies between EU funded polar projects.
- We aim to ensure that EU funded projects have a common voice and to maximise the impacts that projects may have separately.
- We can bring all our expertise together to provide a single channel of policy relevant information to the EC, and other stakeholders as appropriate.
- The Cluster also maintains the legacy of completed projects.
- Expertise are pooled through task groups.
- Past activities have included booths and flyers at international conferences such as the Arctic Circle, breakout sessions at COP23, 2017 (EU-PolarNet, ICE-ARC, EPB).
- Previously EU-PolarNet hosted a page on the Cluster, however now the Communications Task Group co-leads at have created a new website, hosted by EPB and managed by the British Antarctic Survey. This will include updates on initiatives and news on the Cluster projects. This will be developed further shortly.
- EU-PolarNet applied for the Horizon Results Booster (HRB), and EC initiative, which will be used to develop, for the Cluster, a common exploitation portfolio and a communications strategy to improve the impacts of the projects and capacity, through training and documentation on different topics, such as policy briefings. This activity includes representatives of the projects and will take place over the coming week.

- The Cluster is often busy at conferences, and there are sessions of Cluster members throughout this week at the 2020 European Polar Science Week.
- The Cluster achieves its aims through the Task Groups (presenting in the closed section in the afternoon)
 - **Communications and Dissemination** – lead Elaina Ford, BAS (UK) – maintains website, branding, logos, brochures, internal communications;
 - **Stakeholder Interactions** – leads Annette Sheepstra, RUG (The Netherlands) and Kirsi Latola, UOulu (Finland) – coordinates input from indigenous communities and other stakeholder groups;
 - **Data Management** – leads Øystein Godøy, Norwegian Meteorological Institute (Norway), and Stein Sandven, NERSC, (Norway) – sharing project data management plans and expertise and guidance to help projects to make data access “FAIR”;
 - **Education and Training** – leads Josefine Lenz, APECS (Germany), Katharina Beckmann, ULund, (Sweden) – to create joint training activities and synergies between projects, and to keep track of actions on capacity building activities.
- Added values of the Cluster: better collaboration, higher impacts, up scaled efforts, knowledge sharing, less but more effective engagement with stakeholders, greater visibility, and better use of citizen’s money.

3.2.2 The ESA Polar Science Cluster

- By Diego FERNANDEZ (ESA, Italy)
- The ESA Polar Science Cluster is part of the EO Scientific Exploitation, with aims to maximise impact, increasing capacity. This is done in many ways including organising workshops and conferences, education and training activities, scientific toolboxes, new methods and products to increase understanding of the Earth system.
- Improving observational capacity over Polar Regions by capitalising and exploiting on ESA missions, other European and international EO assets. Therefore knowledge and scientific results can be translated to actionable solutions for society.
- There are over 20 projects involved, on Arctic, Antarctica, and third pole.
- There is 1 call open on networking and collaborative research. Activities in the pipeline include a new ITT for ~€2M, tools such as cryosphere virtual lab, training activities, and a MOOC on polar and cryospheric research.
- Projects work towards common goals, such as on snow grain size and albedo, supraglacial lakes, snow melting processes, and surface mass balance, ice sheet dynamics, ocean interactions, etc.
- ESA supports campaigns such as MOSAiC, and international collaborations such as IMBIE (Ice sheet mass balance inter-comparison exercise) and AMPAC (Arctic Methane and Permafrost Challenge)
- The CCI programme provides long term climate data on sea ice, snow, permafrost, glaciers, the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets.
- The Earth System Science Initiative collaboration with the EC has been signed, with a common goal “... to jointly advance Earth system science and its contribution to respond to the global challenges that society is facing in the onset of this century”.
- This is a partnership with ESA’s Future EO and EC’s Horizon Europe, to collaborate on

- In-situ networks/citizen data
 - Enhance models and predictions
 - Interdisciplinary and open science
 - New ICT, cloud computing, AI, etc.
- One of four flagship actions in on the Polar Regions, with objectives to advance our observation capabilities, basic understanding of the different changes taken place in the Polar regions, its interactions and feedbacks with the Earth and climate systems, and expected impacts from regional to global scales.
 - This Polar week has been set up so we can assess the major challenges and how the EC and ESA can work towards these. Call open until 23rd November, AO10461.

Widening the cooperation: the new EU Polar Cluster projects

3.2.3 ECOTIP

- Arctic biodiversity change and its consequences: Assessing, monitoring and predicting the effects of ecosystem tipping cascades on marine ecosystem services and dependent human systems
- By Marja KOSKI (DTU, Denmark)
- We know much about biodiversity and ecosystem tipping points in terrestrial system, but we know very little about it in the open ocean, despite the number of people that rely on fisheries and the carbon dioxide and heat stored in the ocean.
- Therefore ECOTIP will address:
 - Ecosystem tipping points in the Arctic marine ecosystem;
 - It's causes (climate and other anthropogenic stressors);
 - Its consequences for ecosystem services, such as fisheries and carbon sequestration;
 - Adaptation strategies of human systems.
- Geographic focus is East and West Greenland, the Barents Sea and Fram Strait
- Consortium of 15 partners.

3.2.4 FACE-IT

- The future of Arctic coastal ecosystems - Identifying transitions in fjord systems and adjacent coastal areas
- By Kai BISCHOF (University of Bremen, Germany)
- Consortium of 14 partners from 8 countries, €6.4M
- Start date next Monday, 2nd November 2020
- Looking at coastal process in fjord systems and tidewater glaciers
- Aim is to enable adaptive co-management of social-ecological fjord systems in the Arctic, in the face of rapid cryosphere and biodiversity changes.
- Will include scientific data and understanding with traditional knowledge.
- Methods include data science, biodiversity surveys, primary production, tolerance of key organisms, knowledge co-production, stakeholder involvement, policy briefing, modelling.
- Geographic area is Greenland, Svalbard, and Finnmark.

3.2.5 CHARTER

- Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity
- By Bruce FORBES (University of Lapland, Finland).
- Started on 1st August, 50 people on a kick-off online, with partners 25 from 9 European Countries, and Russian and China non-funded partners.
- Aims are to enhance adaptive capacity of Arctic communities to climatic changes.
- This will be achieved through the synthesis of existing datasets from existing projects, modelling socio-economic implications and feedbacks.
- Three central aims:
 - Understand past and ongoing responses of Arctic terrestrial socio-ecological systems to changes in the cryosphere in centennial to millennial timescales,
 - To simulate the future effects socio-ecological change on local communities and livelihoods to 2050
 - Work together with Arctic communities to develop policy pathways on herding, hunting, and fishing.
- The grand challenge is to understand the historic and ongoing Arctic climate and biodiversity change within the modern milieu of overlapping land uses, and with implications for local livelihood practitioners, as well as the general public.
- Participatory methods and co-production of knowledge is central to methods, through workshops, co-development, through proposal and project, of planning and policies, including indigenous scholars in the project and synthesising existing datasets alongside new fieldwork.

3.2.6 PROTECT

- PROjecting sEa-level rise: from iCe sheets to local implicaTions
- By Gaël DURAND (CNRS,IGE, France)
- 25 partners, started September 2020, four years long, €10M www.protect-slr.eu

- Assessing and projecting land-based cryosphere changes to produce robust global, regional, and local projects of sea-level rise (SLR) on a range of timescales.
- To do this PROTECT will better understand the contribution from the Antarctic and Greenlandic ice sheets and mountain glaciers, the largest contribution to uncertainty.
- Reduce uncertainty in models through better understanding the mass loss, reducing uncertainties, and improving modelling tools, in particular accelerated contribution from Antarctica.
- Improved rise and rate projections will be in line with IPCC look to 2100, as well as longer term scenarios.
- These will be designed and tailored to users and stakeholders globally, through an iterative process, co-designed and co-produced.
- Aim is then to have reliable local sea-level rise projections that can be used for risk planning.

3.2.7 ArcticHubs

- Global drivers, local consequences: Tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic “hubs”
- By Pasi RAUTIO (Luke, Finland)
- The strategic goal of ArcticHubs is to develop sustainable, solution-oriented responses for the reconciliation of competing livelihoods and land-use modes in Arctic hubs and their surroundings, whilst respecting the needs and cultures of the local populations
- Intended impact will be long-term sustainability and resilience of future environmental, social, economic, and political factors, in the increasingly competitive and globalised Arctic.
- Hubs include husbandry, forestry, tourism, mining, etc. – which impact wider areas.
- To achieve the goals the project will develop three tools:
 - Public participatory geographical information systems (PPGIS)
 - Guidelines for ‘social licence to operate’
 - Building of future scenarios to be applied in the Arctic

3.2.8 JUSTNORTH

- Toward Just, Ethical and Sustainable Arctic Economies, Environments and Societies
- By Corine WOOD-DONNELLY (Uppsala University, Sweden)
- The project aims to assess the viability of economic development in the Arctic.
- An activity cannot be sustainable if it is viewed by stakeholders as ethically deficient, so JUSTNORTH is assessing economic growth through its ethical sustainability.
- Aim that opinions of those affected by development is a cornerstone of decision-making processes.
- Descriptive, explanatory, and prescriptive objectives, including theoretical investigations of what systems should follow, and through 18 case studies.
- A justice handbook will be used by the case studies. A documentary will be made of the work. The project will provide recommendations for the integrated EU policy
- www.justnorth.eu @justnorth_EU are showing podcasts.

3.2.9 CAPARDUS

- Capacity-building in Arctic standardisation development
- By Stein SANDVEN (NERSC, Norway)
- CSA for 3 years with main objectives
 - Maintain a comprehensive framework for development
 - Identify and document common practices following AtlantOS project
 - Bring stakeholders together to build an Arctic best-practice system
- Two focus areas are fishing in Greenland and declining coal mining in Svalbard being replaced by other activities
- Standardisation requires best practices that sometimes are not written down, through to formal documents leading to national and international law.
- Focusing on natural resource management in Svalbard, Greenland, Russia, to develop an Arctic best practice.

3.2.10 SO-CHIC

- Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate
- By Jean-Baptiste SALLÉE (CNRS, LOCEAN-IPSL, Paris, France)
- 2020-2024 €8M
- Main motivation is that the Southern Ocean (SO) provides large climate regulation, but its role is poorly understood and represented in climate models. The SO contains up to 50% of all CO₂ and 75% of heat that is absorbed by world's oceans.
- To understand the response of policy relevant questions of link of emissions to warming to keep to 1.5 or 2°C we need to understand how much the SO drains carbon and heat from the atmosphere to store deep in the oceans.
- The key processes will be better understood through both observations and numerical modelling www.sochic-h2020.eu @SO_CHIC_EU

3.2.11 TiPACCs

- Tipping Points in Antarctic Climate Components
- By Petra LANGEBROEK (NORCE, Bergen, Norway)
- Coordinating with Svein Østerhus (NORCE)
- TiPACCs has an introductory video on their [website](#), which shows two tipping points:
 - TP1 the Southern Ocean tipping point, from a cold to a warmer ocean
 - TP2 Antarctic Ice Sheet becoming unstable due to reduced buttressing.
- Also investigating feedbacks between the two
- Three numerical ocean models – FESOM, NEMO, MITGCM, and three ice-sheet models PISM, Elmer-Ice, and Úa
- Started August 2019 and will run for 4 years
- <https://www.tipaccs.eu/>

3.2.12 FORCeS

- Constrained aerosol forcing for improved climate projections
- By Annica EKMAN (Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Stockholm University, Sweden)
- A. Ekman is the scientific coordinator, running FORCeS with Ilona Riipinen (coordinator).
- www.forces-project.eu @FORCeS_H2020
- €8M, started 2019
- Whole Earth project improving climate projections of aerosol particles, as these have a significant contribution to radiative forcing. The future development is uncertain but impacts the aims of the Paris agreement.
- The objectives are to:
 - Improve aerosol and cloud processes in Earth System Models (ESMs)
 - Reduce uncertainty in anthropogenic climate forcing
 - Quantify near-term climate responses.
- The uncertainty is due to complicated mechanisms and interactions, with emissions from natural and anthropogenic sources, and interactions with clouds through various processes.
- The project is integrating scientific expertise, methods, and data.
- Focus on Arctic aerosols and clouds in the Arctic through measurements on Svalbard.

Panel Q&A

- How would indigenous communities be included in research and development of the project?
 - K. Bischof (FACE-IT) - one of PIs is an anthropologist, who will take an active role in including the views of the indigenous communities. Stakeholder workshops will be held early in the project to ensure they have an active role in shaping the research questions.
 - B. Forbes (CHARTER): Questions came from the bottom up and were co-developed with indigenous participants in Fennoscandia and northern Russia, also with a social anthropologist and an indigenous project member from Umal. Participatory workshops are planned to assess data and synthesising in an iterative process.
- What other engagement will there be beyond the ESA call
 - D. Fernandez (ESA Polar Cluster): several scientists in ESA projects are also involved in EU Polar Cluster projects, so the community is already working on both sides. All calls of EC and ESA are promoting that collaboration. Some projects are using data. Challenges are how Europe can better capitalise on output of challenges.
- Whether projects expect to use any satellite information, and what hindrances there are to that.
 - G. Durand (PROTECT) – there is no way modelling of ice sheets without EO data, and there are groups in PROTECT to improve the modelling tools, and this is definitely something that is used and needs to be reinforced.

3.3 Closed part of the EU Polar Cluster Annual Meeting 2020

Chair: Nicole BIEBOW & David VELAZQUEZ (AWI, Germany)

Time: 15:30 – 18:00 CET

Rapporteur: Elaina Ford

3.3.1 Attendees:

(N.B. limited number of cameras can be streaming at the same time on gotomeeting)

3.3.2 Welcome words

- by Gaëlle LE BOULER (EASME)
- Gaëlle was very pleased to open the afternoon session, and warmly thanking the EU PolarNet team for organising the clusters day, especially to David. Also to congratulate speakers for morning talks.
- The Cluster is instrumental in facilitating to complimentary cooperation and synergy building between projects.
- Welcoming the new projects to the family. Now we also have the close connection with ESA, which is great in terms of visibility, with at times 340 participants.
- The Cluster will be what we make of it, although there specific work within WP1 of EU-PolarNet 2.
- We all need to take ownership of the Cluster so it is successful. We will also need more regular meetings in addition to the annual meetings, making use of online facilities.

3.3.3 EU-PolarNet 2 role in the EU Polar Cluster

- By Nicole BIEBOW (AWI, Germany)
- Discussions are the area lacking with the virtual meeting, so all are encouraged to participate.
- EU-PolarNet 2 will take over the coordination of the EU Polar Cluster, officially.
- Goals of EU-PolarNet 2 align with EU Polar Cluster, and need the Cluster to deliver.
- We want to convince funders to develop synergies to optimise the use of resources.
- The permanent European Polar Coordination Office
- Task 1.1 Leads Elaina Ford (UKRI-BAS) and Renuka Badhe (EPB)
 - Oversee the Task Groups
 - Organise regular meetings
 - Joint Cluster activities
- Need Cluster involved in EU PolarNet 2 WP2 (stakeholder involvement), WP3 (research prioritisation), and WP5 (policy advice, dissemination, and communication) in particular.
- One member of EU PolarNet 2 Advisory Board will represent the EU Polar Cluster
- Cluster partners should become members of the Polar Expert Group

3.3.4 Common Dissemination Booster – Pre-assessment of the EU Polar Cluster

- By Nicolas FERGUSON, leads Horizon Results Booster for Trust-IT, the Italian SME providing this service.
- Services include community building, social media, web and graphic design, web hosting and maintenance, copyrighting, events management and custom software development.
- Paid by Commission to support activities taking place.
- Letizia Mari, Ruben Tognetti, Zachary Smith will be Trust-IT supporting this.
- HRB Service 1 - Module A – Identification and creation of portfolio of R&I projects
 - 27th October to 30th November 2020

- Sign up to web platform and complete questionnaire, by 3rd November.
Action
- 39 registered so far. Try to find links and collaboration points between projects on activities, outputs and stakeholders
- Impact portfolio dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (PDES) – 120 days December 2020 – Feb 2021 (TBC). Branded factsheets, brochures, videos, can be produced
- Real-case assignment
- Module B – Dissemination Expert Packages (DEPs)
 - Website support, such as results based catalogue

Presentations by the Polar Cluster members on the progress on the four Task Groups:

3.3.5 Communication

- By Elaina FORD (BAS, UK)
- Halldór Johansen (Arctic Portal) was also lead, now looking for a new co-lead.
- New logo created (right)
- New website, www.polarcluster.eu
 - This was created by BAS and Arctic Portal, and is hosted EPB, managed by BAS.
 - This currently is a simple site with portals to the websites of the projects.
 - Main areas to build are the pages for each of the Task Groups
 - Also Collaborative events – this is something we would like to manage in a more cohesive way in the future, proactive rather than reactive.
- Internal communications using RedMine. This has separate pages for each of the task groups, and resources, and a ‘to-do list’ of activities that need to be done. Alternatives include Slack, OneDrive, and can be discussed if needed.
- Social media
 - decided not to have a separate Twitter account but use the hashtags – previously #EUArcticCluster, now #EUPolarCluster.
 - **Action – All projects to use #EUPolarCluster in their social media.**
 - LinkedIn account also now set up. Other social media to be discussed in the future.
- Coordination through EU PolarNet 2
 - Task 1.1 (Elaina Ford and Renuka Badhe) – setting up annual meetings, and definition the vision, mission, and terms of reference.
 - Task 5.2 (Gonçalo Vieira) communicating and advertising Cluster activities, and promoting EU-PolarNet 2 through the Cluster.
- Future work will be on list of mailing lists, newsletters perhaps, task group meetings, and anything else that would be useful to the Cluster.
- Everyone please get in touch if there are any ideas either for the website or other communication activities.

3.3.6 Stakeholder engagement

- by Annette SCHEEPSTRA (RUG, The Netherlands) & Kirsi LATOLA (UOULU, Finland)

- How can the EU Polar Cluster help? - Early information, linking, announcement, sharing, reporting.... Links to communications task group – website, newsletters, etc.

3.3.8 Data management

- By Øysten GODOY (Met. Norway) & Stein SANDVEN (NERSC Norway)
- Also supported by Torril Hamre
- Data value chain:

- Prior planning prevents poor performance!
- Data integration challenges – different or lack of standards, gaps, different disciplines, large range of infrastructures.
- Tasks
 - Terms of reference – draft available shortly on RedMine
 - Purpose and scope – promote and facilitate collaboration within the area of data management between EU Polar Cluster projects.
 - Membership and organisation – representatives appointed by each EU Polar Cluster project
 - Task Group led by a chair and co-chair from different countries, each serving 2 years, change midterm to ensure continuity
 - Evaluate gaps in fairness of relevant data centres. Based on existing deliverables. Compliance checks for FAIRness sometimes being developed.
 - Create guidelines for data centres and data providers.

3.3.9 Interactive discussion

- Discussion on requirements of Communications task group and need for a co-chair and what role would me. Two attendees expressed interest, to discuss further offline with Elaina Ford.
- Future and engagement of Cluster projects. Suggestions:
 - Need spokes people for all projects for the task groups;
 - Need to start planning ahead more often, and form working groups on specific tasks/meetings;
 - Create factsheets on each project;
 - Write position papers with agreement from Cluster on various topics (will have more impact with support from several projects.
 - Create webinars (joint between projects), also a webinar based on all the presentations of the projects.
 - Need to improve engagement of all in the Cluster
 - Create working groups for specific issues/events

- Create mailing lists and make contacts clear on the website
 - Meet more regularly
- Updates to website:
 - Elaina Ford’s task within EU-PolarNet 2
 - Suggestion of having a ‘relay race’/rota of projects searching and finding content for dissemination;
 - Use HRB questionnaire to source information
 - Add tags on website to projects so are searchable;
 - Pick a few issues to champion, e.g. stakeholder engagement, international coordination view
 - Add presentations from this meeting to the website
 - Zenodo community for sharing presentations, infographics etc – Chiara Bearzotti – agreed, Action Elaina Ford.
- Internal communications also need to increase, particularly with the large number of projects we now have in the Cluster
 - We first need to better understand what each of the projects are doing, so we can increase collaboration. For example a joint webinar on the three ecosystems projects.
 - Have pages on website on themes or topics that cross projects.
 - We need to make sure we have the contacts for each task group from each project. This doesn’t have to be the coordinator.
 - Meet for a monthly coffee break
- How would new projects like to be engaged with the Cluster? Projects will need to contribute.
 - FACE-IT - only start next week and would need a little time but would like to be involved;
 - JUST-NORTH – lots to take on for new projects but looking forward to collaborating and opportunities for impact. Also only a few months old.
 - FORCES, 1 year in but keen to be more involved, particularly, in stakeholder mapping but in communication and training in addition.
 - Projects encouraged to review terms of references
 - Note that this doesn’t have to just be the task group representatives but also others in the project.
- Representation of the Cluster
 - Proposal to create a video of the Cluster, Elaina Ford with Nick Ferguson, to put on the website that can be used by the projects.
 - Noted that Nicole Biebow, David Velazquez, Elaina Ford, Renuka Badhe (at least) are available to give presentations on the Cluster at projects’ annual meetings, etc.,
 - Annette notes trust is an important aspect with stakeholder interactions and sharing of lists is therefore difficult, to discuss separately.
- Discussion on the Task Groups and potential new Task Groups
 - Nicole Biebow posed to create a new Policy Advice Task Group. This will be to coordinate policy briefings and advice. This will also reduce stakeholder fatigue particularly in Brussels. This does not mean everything has to be with the Cluster. An email will go out, for people to add their views.
- Communications and dissemination within the EU Polar Cluster

- Beyond communications on cluster activities, also important in terms of planning.
- Collect a load of position papers on various topics
- Nicholas Ferguson - HRB to Everyone. A collective set of policy recommendations from a group of projects can reach policy makers much more effectively than a single project. It has much more impact.
- Any other business
 - Share knowledge on how projects dealing with Covid-19, perhaps a half day meeting in a month or so. Informal Q&A session. **Action Renuka Badhe/EPB.**
 - Noted that the terms of references of the Cluster will be one of the EU-PolarNet 2 deliverables, so projects should think how that should work.
 - Thanks to ESA for hosting the week and all, in particular David Velazquez for his work on organising the meeting.

3.3.10 Next steps and future meetings

- EU PolarNet 2 deliverables:
 - D1.1 – Organisation and minutes of the first EU Polar cluster meeting (month 1) – October 2020 (this meeting)
 - D1.2 - Definition of the vision and mission of the EU Polar Cluster incl. terms of reference (month 8) May 2021
 - D1.6 - First progress report on activities and achievements of the EU-Polar Cluster (month 19) - April 2022
 - D1.10 - Second progress report on activities and achievements of the EU Polar Cluster (Month 31) - April 2023.
- In addition, it was agreed monthly tea/coffee sessions would be set up to enable networking, especially important, as we have not had the chance to meet in person yet (**Action: Elaina Ford**)
- Meetings of each of the Task Groups are needed more frequently than the annual Cluster meetings (**Action: task group leads**).

3.3.11 List of participants

Alberto Zocchi (European Commission)
 Alexander Mahura (UHEL-INAR)
 Amelie Lecornec (So-CHIC)
 Andrea Spolaor
 Anneli Strobel (EU-PolarNet 2)
 Annette JM Scheepstra (EU-PolarNet 2)
 Björn Alfthan (GRID-Arendal)
 Bruce Forbes (CHARTER)
 Chiara Bearzotti (Blue-Action)
 Chiara Venier (Beyond EPICA)
 Christiane Hübner (SIOS)
 Corine Wood-Donnelly (JUSTNORTH)
 David Velazquez (EU-PolarNet)
 Dragana Bojovic (APPLICATE)

Elaina Ford (KEPLER, EU-PolarNet2, ARICE)
Erik Buch (INTAROS)
Gael Durand (PROTECT)
Gaelle Le-Bouler (European Commission)
Hannah Grist (Blue-ACTION)
Heikki Lihavainen (SIOS)
Hugues Lantuit (Nunataryuk)
Isabel Barrio
Jennie Thomas
Josefine Lenz (Nunataryuk, APPLICATE, ARICE)
Joseph Nolan (EPB)
Katharina Beckmann (INTERACT)
Kirsi Latola (EU-PolarNet2)
Ksenia Tabakova (iCUPE)
Larisa Lorinsczi (European Commission)
Leena-Kaisa Viitanen (Nunataryuk)
Lisa Hymas (Nunataryuk)
Margareta Johansson (INTERACT)
Marialetizia Mari (Trust-IT)
Markku Heikkilä (CHARTER)
Marta Terrado (APPLICATE)
Nicholas Ferguson (Horizon Results Booster)
Nicole Biebow (EU-PolarNet 2, ARICE)
Nick Hughes (KEPLER)
Øystein Godøy (APPLICATE, INTERACT)
Paul Overduin (Nunayartuk)
Renuka Badhe (EPB, EU-PolarNet2)
Risto Makkonen
Ruben R. Tognetti (Trust-IT)
Ruth Higgins (INTAROS)
Saša Zavadlav (EC, EASME)
Simon Jungblut (FACE-IT)
Stein Sandven (INTAROS, CARPADUS)
Mikko Strahlendorff
Tina Schoolmeester (Nunataryuk)
Tuukka T Petäjä (iCUPE)
Warren Cairns